

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 15: On the Reproduction Strategy

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Abstract

This tutorial demonstrates new means of defining reproduction strategies that dictate how many offspring solutions should be constructed from each *Parents* object determined during the selection phase.

Keywords: JECDM, EA, evolutionary algorithm, reproduction strategies

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1. Introduction

So far, the framework's implementations assumed a straightforward reproduction scheme: (*Parents* (e.g., two) → one offspring). Since v1.8.0, one may define a custom scheme. For this purpose, an auxiliary *ReproductionStrategy* class (*reproduction* package) is introduced and coupled with *ea.AbstractEA* class (the default highest level abstract implementation of *ea.IEA* interface). The *ReproductionStrategy* class will be expanded in the future. However, for now, it primarily concentrates on defining how many offspring solutions shall be produced from each *Parents* object generated during the selection phase. Such a strategy can be fixed or even dynamic (e.g., expect generating 1, 2, or 3 offspring solutions from two parents selected by a tournament).

The *ReproductionStrategy* provides just a series of instructions, but does not handle the processing. In turn, these instructions are respected in the revised default phases implemented to

be executed in the extensions of the *ea.AbstractPhasesEA* class. Specifically, the extensions/responsibilities can be summarized as follows:

1. The *Parents* class, which serves as a container for specimens selected as parents to be reproduced, must now be instantiated with “noOffspringToConstruct” value. It indicates how many offspring are to be constructed from the selected parents.
2. It is the responsibility of the selection phase to suitably fill the “noOffspringToConstruct”, respecting the instructions imposed by *ReproductionStrategy*. The two available selection procedures *selection.Random* and *selection.Tournament* already handle these imposed requirements (see their common *selection.AbstractSelect* abstract class).
3. If the parameterization is somewhat inconsistent (e.g., the total number of offspring to be produced is odd but the expected number of offspring to be produced from each *Parents* object is even), the above selection procedures may throw an informative exception. Yet, it depends on the configuration of the *ReproductionStrategy* class (it is left for the user to examine it thoroughly).
4. While during the selection phase only information on the mapping (selected parents → the expected number of offspring to construct) is determined, the actual offspring construction is handled during the reproduction phase. The default *reproduction.DoubleReproduce*, *reproduction.IntReproduce*, *reproduction.BoolReproduce*, and *reproduction.ChromosomeReproduce* can now be coupled with various reproduction handlers, each mapped onto a different expected number of offspring to produce. This way, the reproduction process can dynamically adapt to various mappings on demand. If no suitable reproduction

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handler is set, the reproduction phase will throw an informative exception.

This tutorial document provides three example use cases concerning different reproduction strategies:

1. Running NSGA-II [1] with (two parents → two offspring) mapping.
2. Running NSGA-II with (two parents → a random number of offspring from 1 to 3) mapping.
3. Running MOEA/D [2] with (two parents → two offspring) mapping (less intuitive configuration than (1)).

2. Running NSGA-II with (two parents → two offspring) mapping [T]

Source package:
t11_t20.t15_reproduction_strategy.Tutorial1

In this document, only the most relevant pieces of code – i.e., related to adapting the reproduction strategy – are discussed. Note that a dedicated *NSGAIIBuilder* class is used to parameterize and instantiate the algorithm.

First, Listing 1 showcases setting a *StandardDoubleTOReproducer* (TO stands for “Two Offspring”), a reproducer that makes the following two assumptions:

- solutions’ decision vectors are double-vectors,
- two offspring double-vectors are to be produced from two input parent double-vectors.

The reproducer is coupled with an SBX operator dedicated to this processing (named *SBXTO*), a standard polynomial mutation, and a procedure checking the validity of resulting variables.

Listing 1: Instantiating NSGA-II to use (two parents → two offspring) mapping (p. 1)

```
// This example uses a standard reproducer
// that is expected to construct two
// offspring solutions from each
// pair of parents determined by the
// tournament selection. The
// StandardDoubleTOReproducer is used, and
// it can be
// supplied with an implementation of
// ICrossoverTO (TO = two offspring)
// introduced to allow for
// (two parents->two offspring solutions)
// mapping. The SBXTO operator is a
// standard SBX crossover operator that
// complementarily constructs the offspring
// using two parents (see the source for
// details).
b.setParentsReproducer(new
StandardDoubleTOReproducer( //
overwrites the previous setter
```

```
new SBXTO(1.0d, 20.0d), // SBX-TO
crossover
new PM(1.0d / (10.0d + 1.0d), 20.0d), //
PM mutation
// parameters specifying the decision-
// variable bounds and a variable
// repairing procedure:
new Reflect(), 0.0d, 1.0d
));
}
```

Next, Listing 2 illustrates how to define a custom reproduction strategy. Note that the builder object does not deliver a dedicated setter as (i) it is expected that this strategy will not often be adjusted and (ii) a minor degree of access protection is intended to be ensured. Instead, a custom EA params adjuster must be defined, as shown in the listing. This optional adjuster can be implemented to reconfigure the EA being instantiated, but after the default parameterization is done. In this case, a new strategy is set. It assumes a constant strategy that imposes constructing two offspring solutions from each *Parents* object.

Listing 2: Instantiating NSGA-II to use (two parents → two offspring) mapping (p. 2)

```
// By default, the reproduction strategy
// instantiated in the developed EMOAs
// assumes (two parents ->
// one offspring mapping). By adjusting the
// strategy, one can define custom
// mappings. The adjustment can be done
// by an auxiliary "adjuster" object. The "
// adjusters", when provided, are triggered
// after performing the default
// parameterization of the associated
// component. The line below couples the EA
// with a reproduction strategy
// requesting the production of two
// offspring from each parent object
// determined by the selection procedure.
// Note that the selection procedures
// implemented so far in the framework
// respect the constraints imposed
// by the assumed reproduction strategy. In
// the case of not using the below command
// , an exception with the
// "The number of offspring to construct =
// 1 for the Parents object being processed
// , but no dedicated reproducer
// is provided" message can be expected.
b.setEAParamsAdjuster(p -> p.
_reproductionStrategy = new
ReproductionStrategy(2));
}
```

Lastly, Listing 3 demonstrates instantiating and running the algorithm. Finally, the number of performed function evaluations is printed and examined. Since the population size is set to 100 and the method is run for 500 generations, this number should (and is) equal to $50000 = 100 (\text{populationSize}; \text{generation0}) \cdot 499 (\text{theoffspringsize}; \text{theremaininggenerations})$. As explained at

the beginning, the selection phase now checks whether the conditions imposed by *ReproductionStrategy* can be met. For instance, changing the population size in this example to 99 would cause an exception with the following message *It is expected to generate 2 offspring solutions from one Parents object, but it is not a divisor of the expected total offspring size of 99 (reproduction limit = 2147483647; capped to 99), and offspring thresholding is set to disabled.*

Listing 3: Instantiating NSGA-II to use (two parents → two offspring) mapping (p. 3)

```

try
{
    NSGAI nsgaii = b.getInstance();
    Runner runner = new Runner(nsgaii);
    runner.executeEvolution(500);
    for (Specimen s : nsgaii.
        getSpecimensContainer().getPopulation
        ())
        PrintUtils.printVectorOfDoubles(s.
            getPerformanceVector(), 5);
    // Additionally, one can verify the
    // number of performed function
    // evaluations in the following way (
    // expecting
    // 50000 = 100 (population size;
    // initialization) + 499 (remaining
    // generations) * 100 (total offspring
    // size):
    System.out.println(nsgaii.
        getSpecimensContainer().
        getNoPerformedFunctionEvaluations());
} catch (EAException | RunnerException e)
{
    System.out.println(e.getMessage());
}
}

```

3. Running NSGA-II with (two parents → a random number of offspring from 1 to 3) mapping [T]

Source package:
t11_t20.t15_reproduction_strategy.Tutorial2

This example is an extension of the previous. The assumption is now that two selected parents can lead to the construction of 1, 2, or 3 parents (randomly). Listing 4 demonstrates defining and setting a complex reproducer that maintains three reproduction handlers:

1. *StandardDoubleReproducer* handles producing one offspring from two parents;
2. *StandardDoubleTOReproducer* handles producing two offspring from two parents;
3. *StandardDoubleMOReproducer* handles producing three offspring (constructor parameter) from two parents (MO stands for “multiple offspring”).

Note that *DoubleWrappingCrossover* is a simple wrapper for a single-offspring crossover, which is repeatedly executed to construct a desired number of offspring.

Listing 4: Instantiating NSGA-II to use (two parents → a random number of offspring from 1 to 3) mapping (p. 1)

```

// This example provides various
// reproducers. Each is associated with
// producing a different number of
// offspring
// solutions. A suitable reproducer is
// picked during the reproduction phase
// based on the expected number of
// offspring to be generated associated
// with the Parents during the selection
// phase.
b.setParentsReproducer(
    // reproducer that maps 2 parents into 1
    // offspring:
    new StandardDoubleReproducer(
        new SBX(1.0d, 20.0d),
        new PM(1.0d, 1.0d / (10.0d + 1.0d)),
        new Reflect(), 0.0d, 1.0d),
    // reproducer that maps 2 parents into 2
    // offspring:
    new StandardDoubleTOReproducer( //
        // reproducer that maps two parents into
        // two offspring
        new SBXTO(1.0d, 20.0d),
        new PM(1.0d, 1.0d / (10.0d + 1.0d)),
        new Reflect(), 0.0d, 1.0d),
    // reproducer that maps 2 parents into 3
    // (parameter) offspring (MO = multiple
    // offspring);
    // the StandardDoubleMOReproducer is a
    // simple wrapper for the standard
    // crossover operator mapping two
    // parents into one offspring; it is
    // executed a required number of times to
    // produce a desired number
    // of offspring:
    new StandardDoubleMOReproducer(new
        DoubleWrappingCrossover(3,
        new SBX(1.0d, 20.0d)),
        new PM(1.0d, 1.0d / (10.0d + 1.0d)),
        new Reflect(), 0.0d, 1.0d)
);
}

```

Next, Listing 5 defines a dynamic reproduction strategy. It can be done either via using a dedicated static method *ReproductionStrategy.getReproductionStrategy(...)* or step-by-step by using the params container. The uncommented code concerns the latter. First, the code sets the generator (*_noOffspringFromParentsGenerator*) that is executed during the selection phase to determine the expected number of offspring to construct contextually. This implementation returns a random integer from 1 to 3. Then, a flag “*isReproductionStrategyConstant*” is set to false (it must be consistent with the generator). Next, the *_enableOffspringThresholding* flag set to true allows the selection phase to threshold the indications of the

non-constant generator. For instance, imagine that the total offspring size is 10 and the sum of the expected numbers of offspring to construct is 8 so far. Imagine that the indication of the generator in the subsequent selection step is 3. It would mean that the limit of 10 offspring solutions to construct would be violated. If this flag is set to true, however, the selection phase would then reduce the generator's recommendation to 2. Finally, the code instantiates and sets the dynamic reproduction strategy.

As with the previous example, the code finally instantiates NSGA-II and runs it for 500 generations. Imagine, however, that the generator used by the reproduction strategy can return a random integer from 1 to 4, where the latter has no mapped reproducer. If so, the exception may be thrown with the following message: “*The number of offspring to construct = 4 for the Parents object being processed, but no dedicated reproducer is provided.*”

Listing 5: Instantiating NSGA-II to use (two parents → a random number of offspring from 1 to 3) mapping (p. 2)

```

// This example uses a reproduction
// strategy that associates with each
// selected pair of parents a number of 1,
// 2, or 3, which indicates the expected
// number of offspring solutions to be
// produced from the parents.
ReproductionStrategy.Params pRS = new
ReproductionStrategy.Params();
// The contextual generator is responsible
// for determining the expected number of
// offspring solutions to produce
// on demand. This implementation returns a
// random integer from [1, 2, 3].
pRS._noOffspringFromParentGenerator = (ea,
counter, noExpectedOffspringGenerated)
-> 1 + ea.getR().nextInt(3);
pRS._isReproductionStrategyConstant = false
; // auxiliary flag that indicates that
// the above procedure
// is not constant
pRS._enableOffspringThresholding = true; //
// It is recommended to keep this flag
// true in the case when the total
// expected number of offspring solutions
// to generate may exceed the total
// offspring size; if this happens and
// the flag is true, the last indication
// will be suitably clipped.
ReproductionStrategy RS = new
ReproductionStrategy(pRS);

// The above is an equivalent of:
//ReproductionStrategy RS =
//ReproductionStrategy.getDynamicStrategy
//((ea, counter,
//noExpectedOffspringGenerated)
//-> 1 + ea.getR().nextInt(3));

// Set the new reproduction strategy:
b.setEAParamsAdjuster(p -> p.

```

```

_reproductionStrategy = RS);
}

```

4. Running MOEA/D with (two parents → two offspring) mapping [T]

Source package:
t11_t20.t15_reproduction_strategy.Tutorial3

The last example concerns configuring MOEA/D to run with with (two parents → two offspring) reproduction strategy. In contrast to NSGA-II, however, MOEA/D is a steady-state algorithm, which means that it is intended to produce one offspring in one iteration. Therefore, the default method's configurations, done using, e.g., a dedicated builder, set the offspring size to 1. This iteration is referred to in the framework as a steady-state repeat, and a series of such repeats, typically equal to the population size, is considered a generation. Nonetheless, since v1.8.0, defining more complex reproduction strategies is permitted, but one has to be well-acknowledged with the framework's implementation details.

Consider running the MOEA/D for 500 generations with the population size set to 100 (determined by the number of input scalarizing functions used to guide the decomposition-based framework). By default, 50000 function evaluations are thus expected to be performed.

Consider, however, that the MOEA/D is coupled with a two-offspring reproducer, and the adjustment made in Listing 6 is done. It would mean that in one steady-state repeat, 2 offspring solutions are to be constructed and evaluated. Thus, since the number of such repeats equals the population size, 200 function evaluations would be performed in one generation, resulting in 100 + 499 · 200 function evaluations in total. The algorithm would be executable, but typically one assumes that the total number of offspring produced in one generation equals the population size – which does not happen here.

To alleviate this problem, the *ReproductionStrategy* has an auxiliary field “*_offspringLimitInGeneration*” that serves as an additional cap on the total number of offspring that is allowed to be constructed in one generation. It is by default set to a maximal integer value; thus, it is not in effect, and the number of function evaluations in one generation is explicitly controlled by the standard fields (population size and offspring size). Nonetheless, since v1.8.0, the extensions of *AbstractPhasesEA* now report the number of offspring solutions constructed so far throughout the generation, and this auxiliary field is entwined in the processing of the default phases so that:

- If at the beginning of the *AbstractPhasesEA.step(...)* method, the limit imposed by this field is reached, the method skips execution of the phases.
- The default selection phase takes into account this limit when determining the expected number of offspring to construct when preparing the *Parents* objects.

Thanks to the above, the total offspring produced now can be easily capped, which is showcased in Listing 7. Uncommenting its last line of code would result in performing 50000 function evaluations in total.

Listing 6: Instantiating MOEA/D to use (two parents → two offspring) mapping (p. 1)

```
b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy();
b.setEAParamsAdjuster(p -> {
p._offspringSize = 2; // this field
    indicates how many offspring solutions
    are to be generated in
// one iteration (steady-state repeat)
p._reproductionStrategy = new
    ReproductionStrategy(2); // use a
    constant
// reproduction strategy specifying a
    construction of two offspring solutions
    from each Parents
// object selected during the selection
    phase
[...]
```

Listing 7: Instantiating MOEA/D to use (two parents → two offspring) mapping (p. 2)

```
[...]
// So far, it is expected to produce in
    total 2 * 100 offspring solutions in one
    generation (offspring
// size x the number of optimization goals;
    thus, the number of steady-state
    repeats). If one wants to
// cap the total number of offspring to
    produce in one generation so that it
    matches the population size
// (the number of optimization goals), one
    may set the field below (uncomment):
//p._offspringLimitPerGeneration = goals.
    length;
```

References

- [1] Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S., Meyarivan, T., 2000. A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 6, 182–197. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/4235.996017>.
- [2] Zhang, Q., Li, H., 2007. MOEA/D: A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 11, 712–731. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2007.892759>.